

STUDIES ON 'LIPASE' FROM OIL SEEDS. PART VIII. EFFECT OF SALTS ON THE SYNTHESIS AND HYDROLYSIS OF SOME ESTERS BY LIPASE

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The effect of different salts on the synthesis and hydrolysis of some esters by lipase has been studied with a view to obtaining some idea as regards the effect of the nature of the ions on the synthesis and hydrolysis of esters by ricinus lipase.

Rona and Aminon (*Biochem. Z.*, 1931, 241, 460) studied the action of calcium chloride, quinine chloride and strychnine sulphate on the synthesis and hydrolysis of *n*-butyl *n*-butyrate by pancreatic lipase. Ramakrishnan and Nevgi (M.Sc. thesis, University of Bombay, 1947) have found that the synthesis and hydrolysis of esters can be carried out in ether solvent using lipase from castor seed.

The action of the following substances on the synthesis and hydrolysis of esters was studied in order to find out good accelerators: acetic acid, KCN, NaCl, CaCl₂, AlCl₃, Na₂SO₄, Na₂HPO₄, MgSO₄, MnSO₄, BaCl₂ and K₂Cr₂O₇.

EXPERIMENTAL

N/₁₀- solutions of the above substances and the acetone-dried lipase from castor seeds were used for the experiments. Each set of experiments consisted of equimolecular quantities (0.054 g. mol.) of acid and alcohol, 1 g. of lipase, 10 c.c. of ether solvent and 1 c.c. of salt solution. The blank experiment was also carried out side by side. All were kept in the incubator at 37° and at different intervals of time 1 c.c. of each was taken, neutral alcohol (25 c.c.) added, warmed and titrated against *N*/₁₀ sodium hydroxide. The results of the percentage synthesis in the form of difference in c.c. of *N*/₁₀-NaOH between the sample and the blank in case of each salt were calculated. The difference between the two readings shows whether a particular salt is an accelerator or inhibitor depending upon whether the difference is a positive one (showing accelerating effect) or a negative one (showing retarding effect). The results in the form of maximum synthesis reached in each case are given in Table I.

For hydrolysis experiment, each set of the experiments consisted of 0.018 g. mol. of each ester solution, 1 g. of lipase, 10 c.c. of ether solvent and 1 c.c. of salt solution. The blank was carried out side by side. All were kept in the incubator at 37°. At different intervals of time 1 c.c. of each was taken, neutral alcohol (25 c.c.) added and titrated against *N*/₁₀ NaOH. The difference in reading between the sample and the blank shows whether a particular salt is an accelerator or retarder. The results in terms of maximum hydrolysis reached in each case are given in Table II.

From Table I, it can be seen that in general, CaCl₂, BaCl₂ and MnSO₄ are the best accelerators for most of the synthesis experiments and AlCl₃, Na₂HPO₄, NaCl and K₂Cr₂O₇ act as poisons in most of the cases.

TABLE I

Synthesis experiments.

Name of the esters.	Maximum synthesis reached in terms of difference in c.c. of <i>N/10</i> -NaOH between the sample and blank for											
	CH ₃ CO ₂ H	KCN.	NaCl.	CaCl ₂ .	AlCl ₃ .	Na ₂ SO ₄ .	Na ₂ HPO ₄ .	MgSO ₄ .	MnSO ₄ .	BaCl ₂ .	K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇ .	
Methyl butyrate	+2.0	4.7	5.0	6.7	-6.6	-31.2	1.5	2.8	4.2	5.2	-0.4	
Ethyl "	1.4	1.3	0.3	2.5	-1.1	2.3	-0.3	2.8	0.7	0.9	-0.9	
<i>n</i> -Propyl "	1.2	3.2	-2.0	1.8	-1.8	0.4	-2.1	4.8	3.1	13.6	0.4	
<i>iso</i> Propyl "	6.3	2.8	-1.8	2.8	-0.1	1.2	0.6	0.2	3.2	1.6	-3.5	
<i>n</i> -Butyl "	-1.2	-0.9	-2.7	2.7	2.9	0.4	2.2	-3.8	4.9	4.3	0.4	
<i>iso</i> Butyl "	2.3	3.9	-1.3	4.1	2.3	3.8	2.5	1.4	3.8	5.1	-0.5	
<i>n</i> -Amyl "	4.2	3.2	-5.3	5.2	-1.8	0.2	-1.9	1.7	2.8	2.1	-2.7	
<i>iso</i> Amyl "	-4.1	4.2	2.8	3.8	3.9	3.5	-4.1	-1.7	2.2	8.7	-0.8	
Amyl formate	0.3	1.3	-2.1	1.8	-2.2	-1.9	-4.2	4.1	4.6	5.1	0.6	
Amyl acetate	-0.5	-2.1	1.3	5.1	-1.5	1.4	2.3	-0.4	4.2	7.2	-1.2	
Amyl propionate	1.2	3.1	0.5	4.6	-1.8	0.4	1.2	2.9	1.6	5.3	-2.5	

TABLE II

	Maximum hydrolysis reached in terms of difference in c.c. of <i>N/10</i> -NaOH between the sample and blank for											
	CH ₃ CO ₂ H.	KCN.	NaCl.	CaCl ₂ .	AlCl ₃ .	Na ₂ SO ₄ .	Na ₂ HPO ₄ .	MgSO ₄ .	MnSO ₄ .	BaCl ₂ .	K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇ .	
Methyl butyrate	3.7	10.2	4.6	5.2	5.6	5.9	3.5	7.0	9.4	7.0	3.0	
Ethyl "	3.7	1.5	1.3	1.4	1.6	3.7	2.3	3.1	3.9	4.5	0.0	
<i>n</i> -Propyl "	8.9	10.2	8.2	8.5	7.5	0.0	5.9	7.2	8.7	7.7	-1.2	
<i>iso</i> Propyl "	5.2	7.2	5.0	7.2	3.1	2.2	6.5	6.1	9.9	4.1	1.2	
<i>n</i> -Butyl "	-0.7	3.8	2.0	1.8	-0.8	-2.1	-1.7	0.5	1.2	-2.3	-1.8	
<i>iso</i> Butyl "	1.8	4.5	-1.8	1.2	0.4	-1.8	0.0	3.1	4.1	2.1	0.5	
<i>n</i> -Amyl "	2.6	10.7	0.6	3.1	1.6	1.8	1.9	2.5	16.0	2.4	-1.3	
<i>iso</i> Amyl "	4.6	4.9	0.4	3.4	1.0	3.8	2.6	3.5	11.8	1.6	-0.5	
Amyl formate	3.4	1.5	1.8	4.2	0.6	2.6	2.1	2.3	4.6	1.1	0.3	
Amyl acetate	5.3	2.8	-0.3	1.5	1.4	4.2	2.9	3.8	10.6	2.8	1.3	
Amyl propionate	-1.1	3.8	1.2	-2.2	1.4	1.9	3.1	-3.2	11.2	4.2	0.5	

From Table II, it is found that KCN and $MnSO_4$ are the best accelerators for hydrolysis of most of the esters. $K_2Cr_2O_7$ in general has got least accelerating power.

So it can be seen that $MnSO_4$ is a good accelerator for synthesis as well as hydrolysis of esters by lipase and $K_2Cr_2O_7$ in general has got least accelerating power.

In some cases, it is found that one salt, which appears to be the best accelerator in one case, acts as a retarder in other case. Hence, a definite conclusion cannot be arrived at as regards the effect of nature of the salts on the synthesis and hydrolysis of esters by lipase.

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